

Laboratory and field evaluation of bioinsecticides for Colorado potato beetle control

Žigon P., Petek M., Gruden K., Praprotnik E., Modic Š., Dolničar P., Razinger J.

Primož Žigon
primoz.zigon@kis.si

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Introduction

- Colorado potato beetle, *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), is one of the most notorious insect pests of potatoes.
- Larvae and beetles feed on plant tissue causing leaf plant defoliation and stunting.
- The most damaging pest of potato plants since its introduction to Europe in 1922.

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Introduction

Cingel et al., 2016

Mota-Sanchez and Wise, 2021

Biopesticides

<https://ucanr.edu/>

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Research aims and methods

- Alternative IPM strategy on the basis of low-risk plant protection methods.
- Laboratory and field testing of established bioinsecticides and novel non-chemical control measures.
- Evaluation of local entomopathogenic fungal isolates against CPB.
- Studies of interactions and potential synergistic effects of biopesticide mixtures.

Treatment	Active substance
Neemazal - T/S	azadirachtin A (1 g/L)
Laser plus	spinosad (480 g/L)
Laser plus 0,2 dose	spinosad (480 g/L)
<i>B. bassiana</i>	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> (KIS isolates 2300 and 2121)
<i>B. bassiana</i> + Laser plus 0,2 dose	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> (KIS isolates 2300 and 2121) + spinosad (480 g/L) 0,2 dose
<i>B. bassiana</i> + Neemazal – T/S	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> (KIS isolates 2300 and 2121) + azadirachtin (1 g/L)
RNAi	RNAi (dsMESH)
Novodor FC	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> var. <i>tenebrionis</i> (20 g/L 10000 BTTU/g)

Methodology – laboratory tests

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Results – laboratory tests

1. Results of larval direct exposure to biopesticides.

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Results – laboratory tests

2. Results of larval indirect exposure to biopesticides.

Methodology - field tests

- 2020-2022: field experiments conducted in potato field (organic production) at Agricultural Institute of Slovenia, Infrastructure Centre Jablje
- Slovenian potato variety KIS Kokra
- Randomized block design with 6 replicates
- 30 plants/plot = 3 rows with 10 plants/row
- Testing the efficacy of 7 bioinsecticides (and their combinations) against CPB larvae:
 - Laser plus (spinosad)
 - *Beauveria bassiana* (isolates 2300 and 2121)
 - Laser plus + *B. bassiana*,
 - Neemazal T/S (azadirachtin),
 - azadirachtin + *B. bassiana*,
 - RNAi
 - Novodor FC (*B. t. var. tenebrionis*)

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Methodology - RNAi

- Post-transcriptional gene silencing mechanism whereby target gene messenger RNA (mRNA) is neutralized by double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) homologous to the mRNA sequence.
- Use of specific dsRNA to silence CPB mesh gene (dsMESH).

nobelprize.org

Control

Petek et al., 2020

RNAi

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Methodology – field tests

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Results – field tests

Effectiveness of individual bioinsecticide expressed as a reduction in number of larvae (3 and 7 days post treatment).

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Results – field tests

Effectiveness of individual bioinsecticide expressed as a difference in plant defoliation (7 days post treatment).

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Conclusions

- Treatments with spinosad (Laser plus, Laser plus 0.2 dose and *B. bassiana* + Laser plus) provided significantly better control of larval population compared to all other insecticide treatments.
- A mix of both *B. bassiana* isolates outperformed individual isolates and, combined with a 2% recommended dose of spinosad or 100% dose of azadirachtin outperformed those bioinsecticides alone, in laboratory assays.
- The effectiveness of tested bioinsecticides under field conditions was limited.
- Low direct efficiency -> indirect effect on reduced feeding and leaf damage.

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